

Title: Adopting Chaos Engineering in Mobile Robotic Systems Development

Name: Akshay K Jain

Affiliation: Master in Robotics, Robotics Institute, Carnegie Mellon University (PA)

INTRODUCTION:

Mobile robotic systems are decentralized software modules co-ordinating to accomplish a goal. In such a system, Chaos Engineering process can prove highly effective for quality control and assurance.

AIM:

Evaluate methods of adopting of Chaos Engineering process on software development for mobile robotic systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Chaos Engineering is a proven method of detecting failures in distributed systems. This process for adopted by Netflix development team and has shown numerous benefits on QoS. This helps developers design the system in a way that failures are contained within a subsystem and are correctly handled by other counterparts of the system. This methodology applies to mobile robotics systems very well. Mobile robotic systems are built as a distributed system of multiple vehicles (robots) that coordinate amongst themselves as well as a central server to accomplish a mission. Hence, it is of utmost importance such system architectures are verified by chaos engineering principles with simulation-in-loop and hardware-in-loop testing. This talk sheds lights on how to adopt this process for mobile robotics.

RESULTS:

SWOT analysis report of adopting Chaos Engineering methods in continuous development of software for mobile robotics shows pros and cons of such development process.

CONCLUSIONS:

According to the results of the study, Chaos Engineering have benefits that can certainly increase quality of production software. On the other side, the complexity of robotics systems add significant cost for hardware or simulation in loop testing for full system tests.

KEYWORDS:

Mobile robotic systems, software development, systems engineering, chaos engineering

BIOGRAPHY:

Akshay Jain has had extensive experience of 5+ years in design and development of robotic and automation systems. He graduated from Robotics Institute, Carnegie Mellon and Indian Institute of Technology with majors in artificial being, systems engineering and computer science.

Some of his highlighted projects are - Simulation of under-actuated robots (ETH Zurich), Minimal cost task redistribution, Multi-robot SLAM, Monocular SLAM on Quadrotor (CMU), and ACO Emulation (IIT). At 5D Robotics, he has developed systems for various applications - landmine detection and neutralization, person follow, warehouse AGVs, self-driving cars and forklifts, GPS denied quadrotor follow, LIDAR and UWB based localization, and survey & reconnaissance.